

Supplementary Fig. S1 A Venn diagram depicting the distribution of different thyroid dysfunction diagnoses among women in the study. The shaded gray area represents the 103 women with indications of both hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism at different time points during the study period.

	Normal thyroid function (N = 299) (Reference)	Gestational thyroid dysfunction (N = 13)	Chronic thyroid dysfunction (N = 15)	Both gestational and chronic thyroid dysfunction (N = 17)	P-value (Gestational versus normal)	P-value (Chronic versus normal)	P-value (Both versus normal)	
Age of Diagnosis, mean (SD), years	4.7 (1.9)	4.9 (1.9)	4.8 (1.9)	4.9 (2.0)	0.395	0.565	0.442	
ADOS Comparison Score, mean (SD)	7.0 (2.4)	6.7 (2.1)	6.0 (3.7)	8.4 (2.3)	0.520	0.562	0.009	
DSM A Severity, N (%)	Requires support	35 (0.1%)	1 (0.1%)	0 (0.0%)	0.304	0.344	0.328	
	Requires substantial support	115 (0.2%)	3 (0.2%)	4 (0.3%)				6 (0.6%)
	Requires very substantial support	125 (0.3%)	7 (0.4%)	0 (0.0%)				9 (0.8%)
DSM B Severity, N (%)	Requires support	48 (0.1%)	1 (0.1%)	0 (0.0%)	0.936	0.766	0.381	
	Requires substantial support	150 (0.3%)	9 (0.5%)	4 (0.3%)				6 (0.6%)
	Requires very substantial support	75 (0.2%)	2 (0.1%)	0 (0.0%)				7 (0.7%)
Cognitive score, mean (SD)	76.9 (15.9)	72.3 (10.6)	74.8 (8.5)	77.8 (10.6)	0.485	0.787	0.863	

Supplementary Table S1: Autistic characteristics among children with ASD in the different study group

Supplementary Table S2: Cox regression analysis of various types of thyroid function and ASD risk across ethnicity

Status	Jewish		Bedouin	
	Adjusted HR*	95%CI	Adjusted HR*	95%CI
Thyroid dysfunction (N = 4306)	1.33	0.86-1.66	0.94	0.41-2.17
Hypothyroid (N = 3815)	1.48	0.96-2.84	1.12	0.67-1.71
Hyperthyroid (N = 491)	0.33	0.17-2.99	0.62	0.05-3.81
Chronic (N = 1261)	0.43	0.16-1.17	0.69	0.10-5.03
Gestational (N = 1976)	1.16	0.63-2.12	0.64	0.16-2.62
Chronic and gestational (N = 1069)	2.19	1.28-3.77	2.81	1.58-5.06
Chronic hypothyroid only (N = 1161)	0.45	0.17-1.22	0.67	0.09-2.91
Chronic hyperthyroid only (N = 100)	--	--	--	--
Gestational hypothyroid only (N = 1600)	1.51	0.82-2.76	0.73	0.18-2.79
Gestational hyperthyroid only (N = 376)	--	--	--	--
Chronic and gestational hypothyroid (N = 1054)	2.22	1.29-3.82	2.72	1.58-4.99
Chronic and gestational hyperthyroid (N = 15)	--	--	11.67	1.29-105.83
Subclinical hypothyroidism (N = 2414)	1.70	1.29-2.65	1.05	0.78-2.26
Gestational overt hypothyroidism (N = 388)	2.30	0.95-6.25	1.96	0.74-4.66

*Adjusted for sex, ethnicity, gestational age, maternal age, birth weight, assisted reproductive therapy (ART), in-vitro fertilization (IVF), gestational diabetes, gestational hypertension, pre-eclampsia, cesarean section, assisted delivery

Supplementary Table S3: Autistic characteristics among children with ASD who were exposed to maternal thyroid dysfunction in different pregnancy trimesters

	Normal thyroid function (N = 299) (Reference)	Thyroid dysfunction 1st trimester only (N = 17)	Thyroid dysfunction 2nd trimester only (N = 10)	Thyroid dysfunction 3rd trimester only (N = 7)	P-value (1st trimester versus normal)	P-value (2nd trimester versus normal)	P-value (3rd trimester vs normal)	
Age of Diagnosis, mean (SD), years	4.7 (1.9)	4.6 (2.0)	4.8 (2.3)	4.8 (2.1)	0.601	0.532	0.588	
ADOS Comparison Score, mean (SD)	7.1 (2.5)	7.1 (2.3)	6.5 (2.1)	7.2 (2.0)	0.928	0.548	0.751	
DSM A Severity, N (%)	Requires support	35 (0.1%)	3 (0.5%)	0 (0.0%)	0.234	0.753	0.501	
	Requires substantial support	115 (0.2%)	7 (1.2%)	1 (0.2%)				0 (0.0%)
	Requires very substantial support	125 (0.3%)	5 (0.9%)	1 (0.2%)				1 (0.4%)
DSM B Severity, N (%)	Requires support	48 (0.1%)	3 (0.5%)	1 (0.2%)	0.280	0.189	0.345	
	Requires substantial support	150 (0.3%)	11 (1.9%)	1 (0.2%)				1 (0.4%)
	Requires very substantial support	75 (0.2%)	2 (0.4%)	0 (0.0%)				0 (0.0%)
Cognitive score, mean (SD)	76.9 (15.9)	77.1 (12.1)	77.0 (15.7)	76.2 (13.0)	0.940	0.985	0.762	